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D6.3 Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) Plan

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Abstract

This deliverable outlines EVERSE's initial strategy for communication, outreach and exploitation.

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the communication and outreach strategy for EVERSE project. It lays out an action plan for the consortium partners, aimed at making the project goals and progress well understood by all relevant target groups.

EVERSE uses different channels to reach its diverse target groups:

- ▶ Project website
- ▶ Social media channels
- ▶ Scientific publications
- ▶ Project events
- ▶ Newsletter

This strategy is enabled by Work Package 1 (WP1) (Framework of the European Network of Research Software Quality). This work package aims to establish a collaborative framework for enhancing the quality of scientific software and code. This framework will be community-led and inclusive, engaging researchers, software developers, and other stakeholders within the research community. It will facilitate effective collaboration and communication among these groups, laying the groundwork for the development and implementation of best practices and standards for evaluating, verifying, and improving the quality of scientific software and code.

Lastly, this deliverable outlines an exploitation plan, to ensure sustainable use of its assets.

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents EVERSE's strategy to promote the project and to reach out to relevant stakeholders. It sets out an action plan to be implemented by the consortium partners, led by work package (WP) 1 leader, CERN.

This deliverable has the specific objectives to:

- ▶ Define dissemination and communication goals.
- ▶ Describe the target audiences to which the dissemination and communication activities are directed.
- ▶ Set out a dissemination and communication action plan concerning progress and results of the project.
- ▶ Present the respective dissemination and communication channels, tools and organisation structures.

The deliverable is directed by the EVERSE consortium partners, as well as the wider EOSC community.

This deliverable will always be available in the internal repository "Consortium\3.Deliverables\".

2 Outreach and communication strategy

This chapter elaborates on the concrete strategy to reach out to stakeholders and communicate EVERSE project's key messages. We firstly describe the communication and dissemination goals and objectives before exploring the stakeholder groups the project aims to reach.

2.1 Goals and objectives

The overall aim of the project is to produce a long-term and sustainable improvement in research software quality, enabled through a cultural change in the research software community building and maintenance of this software. Thus, a significant thrust of the project is building the community network and, engaging the stakeholders while targeting groups at all levels, from researchers to policy makers: communication activities are an essential and intrinsic high-level activity of the project across all work packages. EVERSE will bring the community together through dissemination and communication activities of all types, from advertising the existence of the community, building and exposing the RSQkit knowledge hub as a primary resource, showcasing successful projects, and through the offerings of training and workshops on a broad range of topics. In addition, we aim to organise a series of event on Software and Computing in Science, to fill the gap in raising awareness of the importance of software and computing in science and the project will evaluate the idea alongside the project and host such a conference if needed.

Dissemination Objectives:

Community building: since the project is intending to bring about long term and sustained cultural changes within the science community in relation to software quality and the scientists and research software engineers (RSEs) involved, it is essential that the project establishes a broad community to support and sustain those changes. The five EOSC Science Clusters (Astronomy and particle physics, environmental science, life science, photon and neutron science, social sciences and humanities), and their recognised synergies and common concerns about software quality, sustainability, and preservation, represent an excellent opportunity for a nucleus to build that community, and to influence the policy makers and managers to ensure that the importance of software is recognised as a first-class activity of doing research.

Raising awareness: building awareness of the project, its aims, and enlarging the community is an important mission. This aim goes beyond simply informing, but rather to also engage other researchers, software developers, experts, etc. to contribute their expertise to share, to learn from each other, and to create a comprehensive resource bringing benefit to the entire community. It is also essential to present the message about the importance of being able to build software of a recognised quality, that enables robust and reproducible research, but that also can be preserved as part of FAIR research output. This message must be reinforced to the policy makers and funders, as well as Research Institutes and RSEs.

Embedding good software practices in EOSC Science Clusters and RIs: Having a common understanding of appropriate software quality and practice across the broad research community is not only of benefit to the research infrastructures RIs themselves, but also to the individual practitioners. Expertise learned in one domain may be more easily transferred to others, widening the career prospects of researchers, software developers and/or RSEs. Many RIs already have initiatives to improve the overall production and management of research software, but the combination of those efforts may help the entire scientific software community make a step-change, and help addressing the need for long-term preservation of software used for research outputs.

Engaging with key stakeholders: Since the EVERSE project is focused on working with research communities to assist cultural change towards software quality improvement, engagement with them has a key importance. This will be achieved through trainings (in person and online), workshops and conferences. In addition, the project will engage with the research performing organisations RPOs and Universities to ensure both appropriate recognition of software as a scientific activity, but also to draw on expertise, and ultimately to demonstrate the needs and benefits of appropriate investment in people and

resources in this area.

Participation in conferences: building on the previous point, broader engagement will be done through a variety of in-person and on-line conferences. These will include purely scientific audiences, as well as those related to open science in general. Engagement with policy makers and funding agencies is also essential, in order to ensure the fundamental support for the change in attitudes we are proposing to address.

Post project action planning: To ensure the long-term impact and sustainability of our efforts, we seek to establish a dedicated organization, a Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence, sustained by the EOSC Science Clusters. EVERSE will define the structure and operational framework for this institute.

2.2 Target Groups

Target groups for specific actions: the Science Clusters, their RIs and others, as well as individual researchers, scientists, RSEs, research infrastructure staff. It is also important to reach students in science who learn computing and software as part of their scientific education, as well as the academics who manage many of these researchers.

The main stakeholders for these actions are those groups that will benefit: the Science Clusters, and their RIs, Research Performing Organisations, the policy makers and funding agencies, and the general public (for example through citizen science).

Target Persona	Description	How to involve	Power	Interest
Science Cluster	Science Clusters in Europe are collaborative groups of Research Infrastructures organized into five domains to enhance data accessibility, interoperability, and open science practices through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).	A science cluster will get involved by collaborating with other research infrastructures to enhance software quality, develop interoperable tools, and contribute to improving research software sustainability and excellence.	High	High
Research Institute	A research institution is a public or private organization dedicated to conducting research to address real-world challenges.	A research institute will get involved by sharing expertise, participating in joint projects, and adopting best practices to enhance the quality and sustainability of research software across Europe.	Low	High
Student	A student is a person engaged in learning, especially one enrolled in a university.	A student will get involved by participating in training programs, contributing to software development projects, and learning best practices for research software quality and sustainability.	Low	High
Research Software developer	A research software developer creates and maintains software tools	A research software developer will get involved in the development of high-	High	High

	and applications to support scientific research and data analysis.	quality, interoperable research software, collaborating on best practices, and participating in community-driven projects aimed at software excellence and sustainability.		
Researcher	A researcher systematically investigates and studies materials and sources to establish facts and reach new conclusions in a specific scientific field.	A researcher will get involved by collaborating on the development and improvement of research software, participating in training programs, and implementing best practices for software excellence and sustainability in their work.	Low	High
Infrastructure Provider	An Infrastructure Provider offers essential computing, networking, and storage resources to support various digital services and applications.	An infrastructure provider will get involved by offering essential computing resources, supporting the integration of research software, and facilitating the development of robust and sustainable software solutions.	High	Low
Help Desk operator	A Help Desk Operator assists users by providing technical support and troubleshooting for software, hardware, and network issues.	A Help Desk Operator will get involved by providing technical support for research software issues, assisting users with software tools, and helping to ensure smooth and efficient use of research software within the network.	High	Low
Funder/Policy maker	A Funder/Policy Maker allocates resources and establishes guidelines to support and shape research, development, and implementation within specific sectors or areas (or national or international level).	A Funder/Policy Maker will get involved in EVERSE by allocating resources, setting priorities, and establishing policies that support the development, maintenance, and adoption of high-quality research software across the community.	High	Low
Trainer	A trainer's responsibility is to educate and equip individuals with the skills and knowledge necessary for their professional development and effective performance in specific	A Trainer will get involved by delivering educational programs and workshops to improve researchers' skills in using and developing high-quality research software, and	High	High

	tasks or roles.	promoting best practices in software development and management.		
Industry	Industry refers to the sector of the economy engaged in the production, processing, and distribution of goods and services, often characterized by its commercial and operational activities.	Industry will get involved by partnering with research institutions to provide expertise, resources, and real-world applications that enhance the development and deployment of high-quality, sustainable research software.	High	High

Table 1. Target groups

2.3 Bidirectional partnerships with stakeholder communities drives development

Table 1 shows how EVERSE is connected to ongoing EC projects and other global efforts.

EOSC Links	
Description	Link / Alignment / Asset leveraged
EOSC Association Task Forces	Direct connection to Infrastructures for Quality Research Software (BSC, FAU, UPM, ARC, HZDR, NLeSC, ELIXIR, UEDIN) Direct connection to the Researcher Careers, Recognition and Credit Task Force (CERTH)
EOSC-Synergy	BSC led the representative use-case for Life Sciences on the joint work for developing software quality indicators and its evaluation. It also facilitates the connection of a specific service (OpenEBench) to an EOSC service (EUDAT B2Share) to facilitate long-term data sustainability, crediting and recognition.
EOSC4Cancer	Led by BSC with strong involvement of CERTH and ELIXIR-Hub, EOSC4Cancer aims to pave the way for cross-European federated and transparent analysis of cancer-related data through analysis methods and protocols that fully adhere to the FAIR principles. EOSC4Cancer will adopt the best practices for research software gathered in EVERSE and follow the research software journey for specific software component cases.
EOSC Future (INFRAEOSC-03 2020)	Alignment and two-ways feedback loop in terms of best practices within Virtual Research Environments being deployed in EOSC. Concrete software use cases from EOSC-Future Science Projects in WP4 and WP6.
GraspOS (EOSC HE project)	GraspOS (led by ARC) aims to develop, assess and put into operation an open and trusted federated

	infrastructure for next generation research indicators, offering data, tools, services and guidance to support and enable policy reforms for Open-Science-aware, responsible research assessment at researcher (individual/group), institutional, organisational and country level.
Horizon Europe Projects	
Description	Link / Alignment / Asset leveraged
TIER2(HE project)	TIER2 focuses on epistemic diversity by selecting three broad research areas (social, life & computer sciences) and two cross-disciplinary stakeholder groups (research publishers/funders) to systematically investigate reproducibility across contexts and to design, implement and assess systematic interventions addressing key levers of change. TIER2 targets to boost reproducibility knowledge, create tools, engage communities, and implement interventions across different contexts.
FAIR-IMPACT	FAIR IMPACT aims to create a FAIR data management cycle starting with real-life use cases in four different domains. Tasks led by SSI, UPM and UNIMAN are describing best practices for FAIR assessment of research software, semantic artefacts and Research Objects. This will enable discovery and interoperability of federated research objects across different scientific communities
Initiatives	
Description	Link / Alignment / Asset leveraged
HEP Software Foundation	Particle Physics initiative on fostering common software techniques, quality, common solutions and tools. Includes training, schools, and outreach activities. Also links to industry and academia to address recognition and rewarding.
SMARTHEP European Training Network	Software developed by Early-Stage Researchers will be tested as part of the pilots
Society of Research Software Engineering, International RSE and the various national RSE associations	SSI was instrumental in the founding of SocRSE, the largest and leading community group for RSEs. Direct connections to Soc-RSE, NL-RSE, de RSE, UKRSE
Global Efforts	
Description	Link / Alignment / Asset leveraged
Language Technology (associations/networks concerned: META-NET, BDVA, CLARIN,	Through projects in Clusters 2 and 4 HE (DATA, HUMAN, PPPA): Humane AI Net, European Language Equality, High-performance Language Technology, RESQ+, MEMORISE, Language Data Space). Assets:

DARIAH, EHRI)	text and multimedia processing software, AI models for multimodal analysis, repository LTP solutions, indexing/search aggregators, PID assignment, SSO and metadata harvesting solutions.
Research Data Alliance (RDA)	Direct participation in RDA. RDA Working Groups can be used as a forum for technical discussions related to research software quality, special consideration will be given to the Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions (RDA TIGER)
Research Software Alliance (ReSA)	SSI (UEDIN, UNIMAN) and NLeSC are founding members of ReSA, and have led on ReSA-supported initiatives such as FAIR4RS and ADORE.software.

Table 2. Established EVERSE links and alignment with ongoing EC projects and other global initiatives

Global engagement

Global engagement will be achieved through our close partnership with the Science for Africa (SFA) foundation. SFA Foundation (<https://scienceforafrica.foundation/>) is a pan-African, not-for-profit, public charitable organisation that supports, strengthens, and promotes science and innovation in Africa, governed by a multi-specialised Board of Directors of scientists and management professionals drawn from across and outside Africa. It is committed to improving the quality of lives of African people and to promote the uptake of research in communities, industry, and the public sector. SFA serves the African research ecosystem by, a.o., building and reinforcing environments that are conducive for scientists to thrive and produce quality research that generates new, locally relevant knowledge.

SFA Foundation has started implementing plans that will establish a Pan-African community of practice (CoP) for RSEs. The goal of the initiative is to enhance the quality and impact of research software and to support the development of a vibrant and inclusive community of practice for RSEs. This will be achieved through the creation of an African led community of practice for RSE communities, the building of necessary skills and training for RSEs, engaging in policy work to support the growth of the field, the development of necessary infrastructure to support RSE work, and the creation of incentives towards the field of research software engineering in Africa.

SFA Foundation, as part of building the proposed CoP, jointly with EVERSE will facilitate a session during one of the annual convenings and as an activity, targeted at providing direct links with the African community of 16 organisations and networks to ensure coherence and enhance the impact of EVERSE (WP1). By supporting the engagement with various groups and communities that have a good history of engagement with open-source software or research communities in Africa, SFA Foundation will underpin engagement with global communities and promote the south-to-north and north-to-south collaboration which are key to achieving inclusive policies and interventions focused on RSEs. The activity can involve additional aspects of discussion in the proposal such as identifying existing practices for evaluating and improving the quality of research software (WP2).

This effort will be complemented by the global collaborations by the various science clusters. For example, SKAO (<https://www.skao.int/en>) has a global footprint and consists of the SKAO Global Headquarters in the UK, the SKAO's two telescopes at radio-quiet sites in South Africa and Australia, and associated facilities to support the operations of the telescopes. More broadly, all the Clusters have RIs that are global in nature, and will engage with that international and global

audience, to share expertise and collaborate on similar and/or related initiatives.

EOSC Science Cluster	EVERSE connection	Community connection
ENVRI	UvA	ENVRI-HUB (knowledge base, search engine and training platforms), and biodiversity communities.
EOSC-Life	ELIXIR, UNIMAN, BSC	ELIXIR is a European Inter Governmental Organisation of 23 Member States which coordinates the EOSC Life cluster project, which brings together 13 life science Research Infrastructures. EOSC Life has led the development of the tools collaboratory including WorkflowHub for registering workflows comprising bioinformatics software and other services around software packaging and annotation.
ESCAPE	CERN, CNRS, FAU, SKAO	High Energy Physics Software Foundation (HSF) collaboration to foster best practices, training, summer schools, common tools and reusable software solutions in particle physics. ESCAPE OSSR (software repository, training collection, best practices in software). Existing efforts in career rewarding and development.
PANOSC	HZDR	Community of large-scale infrastructures (LEAPS, LENS), HIFIS RSE Cluster (research software directory, software development repositories, CI/CD), InvenioRDM
SSHOC	LINDAT / CLARIAH-CZ (CU)	Language resources, natural language processing tools, repository solutions, tools for research in Digital Humanities, connection to SSHOC, CLAIRN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, and the EHRI EU community

Table 3. EVERSE presence across the five EOSC Science Clusters

3 Outreach and communication channels

This chapter outlines the channels EVERSE project leverages for its communication and outreach, starting with its visual identity (Chapter 3.1), the promotional printed material (Chapter 3.2), describing the project website and social media channels (Chapter 3.3), project events (Chapter 3.4) and newsletter (3.5).

3.1 Logo, style guide and project templates

The visual strategy for the dissemination campaign adheres to the co-branding guidelines for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects¹, as proposed by the EOSC Association. The documents outline the main and alternate colour schemes, typeface, logo usage, and the inclusion of the EU emblem for consistency in all campaign communications.

An internal EVERSE logo was created according to these co-branding guidelines before the kick-off meeting. An accompanying design manual applies the guidelines to EVERSE, illustrating the EVERSE logo versions and its different use cases.

In accordance with these EVERSE colour scheme and logo, a set of Microsoft Word and PowerPoint templates was created for deliverables, other project documents and project presentations.

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Abstract

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¹ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-09/EOSC%20Co-Branding%20Guidelines%20for%20HE%20INFRAEOSC%20Projects_HR.pdf

Milestone#:

WP#:

Milestone Title:

Due date:

Lead Beneficiary:

Lead Author:

<p>Date of completion</p> <p>Means of verification</p>	<p>Milestone delayed</p> <p>Problems encountered and solutions recommended</p>
<p>Partners involved</p>	<p>Next actions/steps</p>

3.2 Promotional printed material

During M1 CERTH printed promotional material, that was shared during the Kick-off Meeting in March 2024.

https://everse.software/promotion/EOSC_EVERSE_Brochure.pdf

https://everse.software/promotion/EOSC_EVERSE_Poster.pdf

https://everse.software/promotion/EOSC_EVERSE_Rollup.pdf

3.2.1 Use of QR codes on dissemination materials

QR codes combined with persistent links (such as the ones provided by [Linktree](#)) offer an efficient and modern tool for project dissemination by streamlining access to a wide array of resources through a single scan. This QR code can be easily inserted (as an image) on posters, slides, documents, printed material, etc.

This approach enhances user engagement by providing instant access to a curated list of links, making it easier to share updates, documents, and any sorts of outreach material in one place. Further, kindly note here that one can constantly update the links (delete current, insert new etc.) without having to change the QR sketch. The simplicity of scanning a QR code offers a user-friendly, cost-effective, and visually appealing method to distribute information across diverse platforms and audiences, ensuring broader and more impactful outreach.

Further, it could be also useful if EVERSE partners, participate in more than one projects, and wish to disseminate all of their projects, current initiatives etc., in a presentation for example, under one link, without limitations.

3.3 Project website and social media channels

3.3.1 Project website

As part of the communication and dissemination goals of the project (as set out in WP1), CERN has created a dedicated website located at <https://everse.software/>

The EVERSE website is tailored to researchers and educational organizations. Its primary goal is to increase awareness of the project's progress and serve as a source of information for stakeholders interested in learning more about the project. The website targets the research community as its primary audience, but affiliated entities and other participants can also benefit by staying informed about the project's progress through regular updates. The structure (and content) of the website is in its current status and can be changed/adapted during the course of the project.

Landing page

The landing page of a website serves as the initial point of contact for visitors, providing them with a comprehensive overview of the project and its offerings. It features a user-friendly navigation menu with tabs for information about the project, its use cases, recent news and events, and technical work packages.

The design of the landing page is intuitive and easy to navigate, with clear headlines and a direct link to the project's social media as well as newsletter subscription page for regular updates and engagement.

EVERSE [About](#) [Services](#) [Training](#) [Resources](#) [Participate](#) [News](#) [Q](#) [☾](#)

European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence

High Quality Research Software for the Communities by the Communities

Software for the Communities by the Communities

The EVERSE project aims to create a framework for research software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities, in pursuit of building a European network of Research Software Quality and setting the foundations of a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence.

About

The 'About' section has ten subheadings for information on the 'Objects', 'Consortium', 'Scientific Advisory Board', 'Workpackage Overview', 'WP1-Network', 'WP2-Network', 'WP3-Tools and Services', 'WP4- Pilots and Drivers', 'WP5- Capacity and Recognition' and 'WP6- Project Management'.

Services

The 'Services' section has one subheading for information on the 'Research Software Quality Kit (RSQkit)'. The framework for research software excellence will incorporate aspects involving community curation, quality assessment, and best practices for research software. This collective knowledge will be captured in the Research Software Quality toolkit (RSQkit), a knowledge base to gather and curate expertise that will contribute to high-quality software and code across different disciplines.

Training

The 'Training' section has one subheading with the implemented and the upcoming training events.

Resources

The 'Resources' section has three subheadings which include the presentations, the visual identity and the templates of the promotional material.

News

The News page on the website features updates on the project in chronological order, including information on the project start, kick-off meeting, social media presence and events.

3.3.2 Social media channels and platforms

By leveraging the power of social media, the objective is to reach a broader audience and inform them about the various initiatives and efforts undertaken by EVERSE. This transfers the consortium messages during the stages of the project using eye-catching graphics, compelling posts, and engaging content. This approach will maximize involvement by directing as many people as possible to the project's website. Furthermore, this would enable the target to connect with other EU software-related projects by sharing their contents on the EVERSE channels.

Project related social media accounts have been created on three social media channels and two platforms so far: namely, X (ex-Twitter), LinkedIn, Fosstodon, Zenodo and GitHub at the start of the project. All partners are involved in these accounts to frequently share the consortium activities and the key outcomes achieved. Depending on the performance and traction of activity on the platform, a channel can be taken out of commission or added.

Social media channels	Account Name	URL
-----------------------	--------------	-----

X (formerly known as Twitter)	Eosc_everse	https://twitter.com/eosc_everse
LinkedIn	Eosc-everse	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-everse
FOSStodon	Eosc_everse	https://fosstodon.org/@eosc_everse
Platforms	Account Name	URL
Zenodo	everse	https://zenodo.org/communities/everse/
GitHub	EVERSE	https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware

Table 4. EVERSE social media accounts and platforms

During the lifetime of the project, social media will be used as a key distributor of the project messages. Therefore, key project milestones and planned events will be further posted through social media campaigns. The two objectives behind this are to engage the targeted community and to showcase the project's achievements at each stage.

A social media campaign differs from routine project status updates in that partners are provided with comprehensive materials to create their own posts, rather than simply reposting content from the official project accounts.

Work Package Leaders will be requested during the Management Board meetings to identify any relevant information regarding their WP progress that shall be published on the website and/or posted on the social media accounts. Any changes in official partner social media accounts, as well as contact persons for communication issues, should be communicated immediately to CERN: sanje.antona.fenkart@cern.ch with cc CERTH fpsom@certh.gr.

3.4 Events

EVERSE project will host its own and also participate in external events. This will fulfill the both goals of reaching out to stakeholders and participating to the academic body of knowledge.

Event name	Event date	Venue	Comments	Website
WLCG/HSF Workshop	13-17 May 2024	Hamburg, German	Presentation of EVERSE project	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1369601/
ELIXIR All Hands 2024	10-12 June 2024	Uppsala, Sweden	Presentation of EVERSE as part of the ELIXIR Tools platform Mini-symposium.	https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-all-hands-2024

Belgrade Bioinformatics Conference – BelBi	17-19 June 2024	Belgrade, Serbia	Presentation of EVERSE project	Home - BelBi 2024 (bg.ac.rs)
2024 Coordination meeting of EOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe	20-21 June 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation of EVERSE project	https://eosc.eu/events/2024-coordination-meeting-of-eosc-related-projects-funded-under-horizon-europe/
2024 International Research Software Funders Workshop	9-10 September 2024	Uppsala, Sweden	EVERSE Satellite event	https://adore.software/2024-international-research-software-funders-workshop/
EOSC Symposium 2024	21-23 October 2024	Berlin, German	EVERSE is a co-organizer/submitted	https://eosc.eu/events/eosc-symposium-2024/

Table 5. List of potential events to attend

3.5 Newsletter

In order to ensure project efficiency, transparency, and visibility among its members, a periodic-currently planned to be quarterly- newsletter will be distributed to the consortium.

The newsletter will gather updates on:

- ▶ The overall outcomes of the project
- ▶ The progress of each Work Package
- ▶ Upcoming meetings
- ▶ Latest project activities and social media messages
- ▶ Calls for participation in social media campaigns
- ▶ Calls for identification of external events for dissemination
- ▶ Other

Coordination will be held by CERTH, with the support of CERN and BSC.

4 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- Logo creation and communication templates (e.g. standard document templates for deliverables, reports, presentations etc.), brochures, flyers, exhibition booth. (Target: Community at large, public)

Deadline: Until 31/05/2024

- Project Web portal: this will be the face of the project, the entry point for ALL partners, stakeholders, and the general public. It will have a wide range of functionalities with components maintained and distributed from across the project. It will feature both “push and pull” marketing strategies:
 - link to the EVERSE social media accounts, e.g. on Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn and Twitter,
 - “boosting” specific social media posts, and target specific audiences based on appropriate demographics,
 - contain popular features such as event calendar, news, public resources area,
 - link to the EOSC catalogues of services and to the EVERSE RSQkit knowledge hub

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- News from the EVERSE project will regularly be submitted to, and further distributed via, the Newsletters of all involved Science Clusters as well as all relevant European Science Societies Newsletter and other appropriate outlets. (Target: scientific community at large, policy makers, funders)

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- Publications in scientific and technical peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, monographs etc. in Open Access formats, journals, and repositories. (Target: scientific community, RSEs, researchers, developers, RPOs)

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- Other project deliverables, and reproducible code from the pilots, made available in open online repositories, e.g. Zenodo. (Target: Policy makers, funders, RPOs, Clusters)

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- Comprehensive review of target audience, (measurable) goals, communication partners, communication channels, and tools.

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- RSQkit knowledge hub: this will be the repository of all of the accumulated and curated knowledge as the result of the project. It will be linked (onboarded) to the EOSC portal and the EVERSE project web, and will contain the knowledge bases of curated best practices, software and tools for software quality improvement, training courses and materials, documentation. It will be set up early in the project. (Target: Researchers, RSEs, RPOs, RIs/Clusters, scientific community at large).

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- In addition, certain training materials will be made available in open online repositories e.g. TESS, OpenPlato (Target: science communities, researchers, RSEs)

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- EVERSE will produce high quality video products and webinars made available via the portal and through a dedicated YouTube Channel. They will be curated in the RSQkit. (Target: Researchers, RSEs, RPOs, RIs/Clusters, scientific community at large). Among the videos, we will include user stories on the pilot cases from the Science Clusters throughout the process of implementing EVERSE recommendations.

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- An EVERSE exhibition booth will be present at high-level meetings and key events. Meet and greet opportunities with refreshments will be organised. (Target: Scientific community, RSEs, researchers, policy makers)

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- EVERSE will encourage its expert members to participate in relevant national, European, or international working groups and committees, such as the RDA, ReSA, and others.

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- For Policy makers and funding agencies: Policy briefs, responses to consultations and requests for information, presentations will be prepared.

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

- Dissemination impact metrics: definition of quantitative KPIs, monitoring of bibliometric impacts, and access to digital objects created in the project. (Target: Policy makers, funders, project members)

Deadline: Throughout the entire project

